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Chapel Royal links in Oxford The Music of Captain Henry Cooke at Christ Church

Within the Western Musical Canon, the composers of The English Restoration School – such as Pelham Humfrey, John Blow, and Henry Purcell – are often held considered jewels of musical achievement. The prodigious nature of this set of composers cannot be denied, and many achieved contemporary renown at young ages. However, the thread that links the composers above, amongst others, has been somewhat relegated to the footnotes of musical history; this being Captain Henry Cooke (*d.*1672). Cooke was appointed ‘Master of the Children of the Chapel Royal’ with immediate effect following Charles II’s restoration to the throne and quickly set to work re-populating the chapel with talent.¹

The English Civil Wars and Commonwealth (1642-60), which had effectively stopped professional music-making in sacred environments for around 16 years, had made this task significantly more difficult than for any previous occupant of that position. As many of the original adult choir members were simply reappointed,² the sourcing of a treble line became the crux of Cooke’s challenge. The results of Cooke’s pedagogy show that the task was deftly handled, through a combination of exercising the pressing system, granted by his position, as well as his clear ability to identify promising choristers.³

¹ For Cooke’s appointment as ‘master of the boyes in ye private musick’, see Andrew Ashbee, ed., *Records of English Court Music (RECM)*, 9 vols (Snodland; Aldershot: Scolar Press, 1986-96), i, 4. His appointment as master of the Children of the Chapel Royal is never explicitly stated, succeeding the position from Thomas Day, who had died during the years of Commonwealth. See Ashbee, *RECM*, i, 6.

² Samuel Teague, ‘Piercing Through the Gloomy Silence: Musicians’ Livelihoods in Civil War and Commonwealth England (c.1642-1660)’, *BFE/RMA Research Students’ Conference 2021*, University of Cambridge (Online), 13 January 2021.

³ Cooke had the right, as master of the Children, to recruit (or more accurately, ‘press’) choristers from other cathedrals and chapels into service with the Chapel Royal. Documented in the court papers are expenses for journeys to Newark, Lincoln, Rochester, Peterborough, Worcester, and ‘other places’. Ashbee, *RECM*, i, 19 & 98.

Cooke quickly gathered twelve boys for the Chapel Royal (a number that had remained constant since at least the 1550s)⁴ – many of whom would go on to be figureheads of the English Restoration School.

Little is known concerning Cooke outside the entries included in the *Records of English Court Music*, with further documentary evidence being exceptionally sparse. However, by looking to his extant music, and the manuscript sources in which it is contained, one can begin to uncover several consistent threads. There are sixteen surviving manuscript sources containing Cooke’s repertoire, of which eleven are known to have originated in Oxford. Christ Church was clearly a nexus for Cooke’s repertoire with several of the post-Restoration singing men of the Cathedral serving as the copyists for the surviving manuscripts. These include Richard Goodson Sn, William Husbands, Charles Husbands Jr, and Francis Withy. Today, Christ Church remains a focal point for Cooke’s music, as the library’s special collections hold a majority (7) of the extant manuscripts.

MS	Description	Copyist ⁵	Copying Location	Date Range
Bu 5001	Guardbook	Henry Cooke	London, Chapel Royal	1660-70
DRc MS B1	Organ book	Richard Hosier	Dublin	1665-75
Lbl Add. MS 14399	Pedagogical study book	/	/	1650-77
Lbl Add. MS 19759	Collection of compositions	Charles Campelman	/	1681-5
Lbl Add. MS 29396	Collection of vocal music	Edward Lowe	Oxford	1678-82
Lbl Add. MS 31460	Scorebook of solo voice music	Richard Goodson, William Husbands, Charles Husbands Jr	Oxford, Christ Church	1688-93
Lbl Add. MS 33234	Scorebook of sacred and secular music by English and Italian composers	Charles Morgan	Oxford, Magd. College	1680-82

⁴ *RECM*, vii, 127.

⁵ Responsible for the content by Cooke in the manuscript.

Lbl Egerton MS 2960	Scorebook of sacred and secular music	/	Oxford	1670-90
Ob MS Mus. Sch. d. 217	Miscellaneous notes, scores, and bass parts	Francis Withy	Oxford, Christ Church	1681-1703
Och Mus. 12	Anthems and contrafacta for choir with continuo	Charles Husbands Jr	Oxford, Christ Church	1688-92
Och Mus. 14	Sacred and secular music by English and Italian composers	John Blow	London	1674-75
Och Mus. 22	Scorebook	Richard Goodson Sn	Oxford, Christ Church	1670-77
Och Mus. 49	Composite score of English and Italian vocal music	/	Oxford?	1670-75
Och Mus. 598	Collection of songs and keyboard pieces	Richard Goodson Sn	Oxford, Christ Church	1675-85
Och Mus. 1205 (A)	'Sleep downy sleep' copied in score	Richard Goodson Sn	Oxford, Christ Church	1685-95
Och Mus. 1246	Tenor partbook from Christ Church Cathedral	Francis Withy	Oxford, Christ Church	1670-77

Christ Church Copyists

Four of the Cathedral singing men copied Cooke's surviving repertoire found in the collections at Christ Church, which illustrates (at the very least) that Cooke's music was both known and being performed in Oxford beyond his death in 1672.

William and Charles Husbands were brothers, and both choristers at Christ Church (1673-82 and 1677-84, respectively) before becoming singing men and organists of the Cathedral until their deaths, both in 1692. During their adult years, they were employed to copy pieces for use in the Cathedral, which presumably was the original purpose of Och Mus. 12 and the British Library manuscript Add. 31460.⁶

Francis Withy had a similar career to the Husbands brothers, serving as a singing man from 1670 until his death in 1727, during which time he regularly was called upon to copy music for both the Cathedral and University.⁷ He was responsible for the Bodleian manuscript, MS Mus. Sch. d. 217 (the only Cooke

⁶ John Milsom, ed. 'Mus. 11'. *Christ Church Library Music Catalogue*. 2004; Harold Watkins Shaw, *The Succession of Organists of the Chapel Royal and the Cathedrals of England and Wales from c.1538* (Oxford: The Clarendon Press, 1991), 211.

⁷ Robert Thompson. 'Withy family [Withie, Wythey]'. *Oxford Music Online*, 2014.

manuscript held by the institution) which contains the bass part to the anthem 'Turn thou us, O good Lord'.

Richard Goodson Sn served as a singing man at Christ Church between 1667-81, before succeeding Edward Lowe as Heather Professor of Music.⁸ In 1692, he took up the post of organist at Christ Church which he held until c.1714, when he left his duties to his son, also called Richard.⁹ Two of the Christ Church sources which Goodson copied, Och Mus. 22 and Mus. 598, found their way into the Cathedral via the Goodson bequest, which was made by his son c.1743.

It might be natural to think that the plentiful sources linked to Christ Church would indicate that Cooke himself had a personal link with the Cathedral and/or College. However, one should be cautious in assuming this. Cooke did seem to enjoy what we might consider a moderate level of contemporary fame, at least within certain London-centric music-literate circles. Had he been affiliated with any institution in Oxford following the period of civil war and Commonwealth then one would suspect that this information would have been recorded and already known – the absence of any relevant information, in this regard, is its undoing.

In addition, Anthony Wood, noted antiquary and amateur musician, was a direct contemporary of Cooke and meticulously described his own life in Oxford – his involvement and exposure to the musical scene being a particularly prominent feature. It is just as telling as the lack of official institutional documentation that Cooke is not mentioned in Wood's writings, be that *Athenæ Oxonienses* or his personal diaries. In fact, the only record Wood makes of Cooke is in his manuscript list of musicians, Ob Wood MS D 19(4), where Cooke receives a short entry that in no way indicates personal association between the two. Coincidentally, the manuscript is the single reference to Cooke's potential past as a chorister in the Chapel Royal – which is possible, although a lack of any official documentary warrants further consideration.¹⁰

If one looks in the opposite direction, and considers whether any of the copyists had a connection to Cooke, only one of the four Christ Church men had a direct link to the Chapel Royal: Charles Husbands Jr. He is recorded as having been a chorister in

⁸ An endowed chair within the University of Oxford.

⁹ Robert Thompson. 'Goodson, Richard (i)'. *Oxford Music Online*. 2001.

¹⁰ Cooke's will (Lna PROB 11/343/321) states that he wished to be buried in the cloisters of Westminster Abbey in the same plot as his daughter, Mary, who predeceased both him and his wife (also Mary). The right to have a family member buried in the Abbey cloisters would only have been granted if Cooke had a prior connection to the institution prior to the Civil Wars – it is perhaps more likely that a link exists here, and not with the Chapel.

attendance of the King at Windsor in 1683 (overlapping with his recorded dates as a chorister at Christ Church).¹¹ This stint in the Chapel was, clearly, much later than Cooke's tenure, but would have seen Husbands working underneath John Blow as Master of the Children, thus providing us with the solid link to Cooke and his repertoire. It is also likely that both the Husbands boys would have been exposed in some way to Cooke's other repertoire, as their father (Charles Sn) was a Gentleman of the Chapel Royal contemporaneous with Cooke.¹² In the course of the ongoing research into Cooke, there will be further exploration into the relationships between composers and copyists, in a hope to reveal more about professional musical networks (of both sacred and secular natures) during the early years of the Restoration and beyond.

Christ Church Manuscripts

Of the seven Cooke manuscripts held at Christ Church, none are in his hand, but Mus. 14 is closely linked to him, as an autograph manuscript in the hand of his pupil, John Blow. Having been one of Cooke's earliest choristers, Blow would have had an intimate knowledge of Cooke's repertoire, indicating that the reading in Mus. 14 is close to the original, possibly having been copied from a holograph source that is no longer extant.

Manuscript	Cooke Content	Bequest
Mus. 12	Turn thou us, O good Lord	Aldrich
Mus. 14	Turn thou us, O good Lord	Aldrich/Goodson
Mus. 22	Turn thou us, O good Lord	Goodson
Mus. 49	As on a river's side; Awake my soul; Sleep, downy sleep	Aldrich/Goodson
Mus. 598	Turn thou us, O good Lord	Goodson
Mus. 1205(A)	Awake my soul	-
Mus. 1246	Turn thou us, O good Lord	Christ Church Cathedral, Library

What is possibly most interesting concerning the extant manuscripts held at Christ Church is the fact that, apart from Mus. 1246, none of the items belonged to the Cathedral as an institution, rather belonging to individuals who were members of the choir, which then made their way into the College special collections (rather than returning to use in the Cathedral). John Milsom made mention of this when compiling the digital music catalogue for Christ Church, drawing particular attention to those materials which had been bequeathed to the special

¹¹ Ashbee, *RECM*, i, 206.

¹² It is possible that Charles Sn was among the extraordinary gentlemen of the Chapel, as his appointment is not formally recorded, but he is paid for singing at Windsor on more than one occasion. *Ibid.*, 109, 136, & 143.

collections by the Cathedral, and not external benefactors (who, admittedly, had pre-existing links to the musical life of the Cathedral, in the case of all the individuals above).¹³

As can be seen in the table above, most of the Christ Church manuscripts contain the verse anthem 'Turn thou us, O good Lord', in some form. If Mus. 1246 were not extant, it could be argued that the anthem was only known to some of the Cathedral's singing men and that it was not a piece of regular repertoire at the Cathedral. However, as the piece existed both in the Cathedral's partbooks (tenor, in this instance) and the private collections of the singing men, it can be construed that, at the very least, this piece of Cooke's repertoire enjoyed a reasonably prolonged performance life in Oxford, from 1670, at the latest, until at least 1705.¹⁴

When we cast the net a little wider to consider those manuscripts which are not held by the special collections but do appear to have had their origins at Christ Church, we see a similar case of a prolonged shelf life with Cooke's solo song pair, 'Awake my soul' and 'Sleep, downy sleep'. This pair of songs exist in the scorebook, Lbl Add. MS 31460, which features one copy of 'Awake my soul' and two of 'Sleep, downy sleep' (in D and C minor, respectively). In addition, each of the Cooke pieces are in the hands of different men, all of whom having already been discussed: Richard Goodson, William Husbands, and Charles Husbands Jr – forging a strong link between the repertoire seen in this manuscript, and that contained within those still held at Christ Church.

To be considered further still are the stemmatics of the manuscripts.¹⁵ The songs remain extant in six manuscripts, which in themselves exhibit a clear bipartite division in their readings of the piece. In this division, Lbl Add. 19759, Add. 29396, Add. 31460, and Och Mus. 1205(A) are derived from the same lost manuscript. This lost manuscript is most likely an intermediary source, rather than the original, as the other version of the songs (as seen in Och Mus. 49 and Lbl Add. MS 33234) are both shorter, and therefore may have derived from the original source. Due to the linked nature and provenance of Lbl Add. MS 31460 and Och Mus. 1205(A), it can be

¹³ John Milsom. 'The Repertory of Christ Church Cathedral'. 27 Jan 2009.

<library.chch.ox.ac.uk/music/page.php?page=The+repertory+of+Christ+Church+Cathedral>.

¹⁴ This latter date has been ascertained from the copying dates of Ob Mus. Sch. D. 217, copied by Francis Withy.

¹⁵ The discussion on Cooke's song output – with particular focus on the authorship of 'Sleep, downy sleep' – has been discussed and greatly developed since, see: Samuel Teague, 'A Seventeenth-Century Whodunnit: Reassessing the Ascription of 'Sleep, downy sleep'', *Music, Creativity, and Culture in England, 1642-88*, Conference Address, The Queen's College, 21 May 2022.

supposed that the lost manuscript source on which their content was based was known to at least Richard Goodson Sn, if not William and Charles (Jr) Husbands as well. Whilst it seems likely that Och Mus. 14 was the primary transmission document for 'Turn thou us, O good Lord' (due to the close ties to Blow, and therefore Cooke), the lost manuscript was most likely the transmission source for the songs 'Awake my soul' and 'Sleep, downy sleep'.

From the manuscript materials held at Christ Church, it is clear that Cooke's music saw a prolonged and reasonably successful position within the Cathedral's repertoire until the beginning of the eighteenth century, at least. The fact that the singing men copied the repertoire for both personal and institutional usage also illustrates that, whilst the Cathedral was a centre for the activity, the repertoire was also most probably used within other contexts in the city – possibly at some of the musical meetings documented by Anthony Wood.

Further study is now required on the manuscripts; watermarks, gathering of the quires, etc., in order to provide further methods for dating and ascertaining provenance. It is hoped that these physical attributes of the manuscripts will provide further concrete evidence of Cooke's repertoire in Oxford and solidify the links between the Cathedral and the Chapel Royal.

The beginning of 'Turn thou us, O good Lord'
Mus 14, fol. 139.

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Since February 2022, Sam has also been a member of library staff at Christ Church; granting, much to his delight, ready access to these manuscripts.